

On the Second Postulate of the Special Relativity Theory – the Velocity of the Light Source Relative to What?

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Abstract

The Special Relativity Theory (SRT) is founded on the two postulates. 1. The principle of relativity 2. The speed of light in vacuum is constant c is independent of the velocity of the source. This paper points to a flaw in the second postulate that has been overlooked for more than a century: the velocity of the source relative to what? Imagine a terrestrial light speed experiment. Consider two cases: 1. The observer/detector is at rest and the source is moving with velocity v , relative to the earth. 2. The source is at rest and the observer is moving with velocity v , relative to the earth. According to the principle and theory of relativity, there should be no difference between the experimental outcomes in the two cases. We analyze each of these cases both in the reference frame of the observer/detector and in the reference frame of the source and compare the results with experimental facts. The second postulate is not only in contradiction with the first postulate, but also is in disagreement with experimental facts. We argue that the only way out is to accept the existence of absolute motion. The second postulate should be corrected and restated as: the speed of light in vacuum is constant c independent of the source *absolute* velocity. But then this disproves the principle and theory of relativity.

Introduction

The Special Relativity Theory (SRT) is founded on the two postulates.

1. The principle of relativity
2. The speed of light in vacuum is constant c is independent of the velocity of the source.

The universal thinking within the scientific community is that these postulates are experimentally established facts. However, the first postulate (the principle of relativity) has been and is being challenged by many independent researchers, such as by those still supporting ether theory and by this author himself. The second postulate, unlike the first postulate, is accepted (almost) universally, except for few advocates of the classical emission (ballistic) theory, which are in oblivion today. Therefore, it would be surprising to question the second postulate today. This paper points to a flaw in the second postulate that has been overlooked for more than a century.

The second postulate of the Special Relativity Theory- the velocity of the source relative to what?

The second postulate of SRT states that the speed of light is independent of the source velocity. But there is a flaw in the second postulate: the velocity of the source relative to what?

Consider two cases of a terrestrial light experiment involving a light source and an observer/detector. In the first experiment, the observer is at rest and the source is moving with velocity v away from the source, in the earth's frame. In the second experiment, the source is at rest and the observer is moving with velocity v away from the observer, in the earth's frame. Next we analyze the predicted experimental outcomes based on the second postulate for each case, both in the reference frame of the source (Fig 1a) and in the reference frame of the observer (Fig 1b) and compare the results with experimental facts, as shown in the table below.

Fig 1a

Fig 1b

Assume that the distance between the source and the observer is D at the instant of light emission ($t = 0$). We ignore the velocity of the earth relative to the sun and relative to the ECI frame to avoid complications. Also we assume $v \ll c$, so that $\gamma \approx 1$ and relativistic effects can be ignored.

	Time of light detection τ (assume light is emitted at $t = 0$) (based on the on the second postulate)		Experimental fact (τ)
	In the reference frame of the observer	In the reference frame of the light source	
Observer at rest and light source moving with velocity v directly away from the observer, in the earth's frame	$\tau = \frac{D}{c}$	$\tau = \frac{D}{c - v}$	$\tau = \frac{D}{c}$
Light source at rest and observer moving with velocity v directly away from the source, in the earth's frame	$\tau = \frac{D}{c}$	$\tau = \frac{D}{c - v}$	$\tau = \frac{D}{c - v}$

If the second postulate was correct and compatible with the principle of relativity, there would be agreement in the predicted times (τ) of detection in the two experiments, there would be agreement between the predictions in the observer's and source's reference frames, and agreement with the actual experimental results.

From the above table, we can see that the second postulate is disproved in both experiments. (amber shaded cells).

1. In the first experiment, that is the case of the observer at rest and the light source in motion relative to the earth, the second postulate makes correct prediction that agrees experiments in the reference frame of the observer. However, the second postulate makes wrong prediction in the reference frame of the source. In this case, the light postulate predicts that the speed of light is constant c . However, as can be seen from the table, this leads to a wrong prediction of τ . The correct value of τ can be obtained only by assuming $c+v$ for the speed of light in this frame.

2. In the second experiment, that is the case of the light source at rest and observer in motion relative to the earth, the second postulate makes correct prediction that agrees with experiments in the reference frame of the source. However, it makes wrong prediction in the reference frame of the observer. In this case the second postulate predicts that (in the reference frame of the observer) the speed of light is constant c independent of the velocity of the source in this frame. But we can see that the speed of light depends on the source velocity in the observers frame! The correct value of τ can be obtained only by assuming $c-v$ for the speed of light in this frame.

The only way out is to accept the existence of absolute motion and restate the second postulate as: the speed of light in vacuum is constant c independent of the source *absolute* velocity. But then this disproves the principle and theory of relativity.

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